

The Raised-Fifth Grid: A Unified Tuning for Western and Middle Eastern Modes on a 12-Key Keyboard

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Abstract

This paper introduces a fixed 12-key keyboard tuning based on a single upward displacement of one fifth (and its complementary fourth) by 50 cents. With this minimal intervention, the system enables the realization of a broad range of Middle Eastern modal step patterns (maqāmāt, ajnas, and dastgāh) alongside standard Western scalar step patterns, without dynamic retuning or additional keys. Within a two-octave span, modal structures arise through combinations of whole steps, half steps, and characteristic neutral step sizes ($3/4$ and $5/4$ steps). The tuning preserves the step organization of the modes while acknowledging that traditional modal usage may extend beyond the fixed grid. The system further reveals a unified modal framework in which Western and Middle Eastern modal systems appear as connected regions of a single underlying structure, serving as both a pedagogical and performance model on a single fixed keyboard.

Introduction

Twelve-key keyboard instruments have historically posed a fundamental challenge for preserving modal structures that rely on neutral intervals (150 and 250 cents, etc.), as found in Middle Eastern modes when represented within a 24-ET framework. This limitation has traditionally been addressed either through retuning, the addition of extra keys, or by accepting structural compromise.

This paper proposes a minimal solution through the Raised-Fifth Grid, constructed by raising a single fifth of the 12-ET system by 50 cents. This single modification produces a fixed 10+2 structure consisting of ten unaltered pitch classes and two raised pitch classes. Despite its minimal nature, this grid supports a wide range of Middle Eastern modal step patterns alongside standard Western scales.

The following sections outline the construction of the tuning, the resulting jins and modal realizations, and the corresponding implications for Western scalar systems within this unified framework.

1. Basic Definitions and Notation

The following conventions are used throughout this paper:

Pitch notation. Pitch classes are presented using letter names (C, D, E, etc.).

Raised pitch classes resulting from the 50-cent modification are marked with a small upward arrow (e.g., $E_{\flat}\uparrow$, $A_{\flat}\uparrow$).

Step sizes.

W: whole step (200 cents)

H: half step (100 cents)

3/4: neutral step of 150 cents

5/4: larger neutral step of 250 cents

A2: augmented second (300 cents)

Step pattern. The ordered sequence of interval sizes between adjacent degrees of a mode.

Raised pitch class. A pitch shifted upward by 50 cents relative to its 12-ET position.

10+2 structure (Raised-Fifth Grid). The resulting pitch framework consisting of ten unaltered 12-ET pitch classes and two raised pitch classes produced by raising two pitch classes forming a fifth.

Ajnas. Small modal pitch collections (typically 3–5 notes) used as the basic building blocks of Middle Eastern modal theory.

Maqamat. Modal systems in Arabic music theory, formed through the combination and development of ajnas.

Dastgah. The modal system of Persian classical music, analogous in function to maqam but with its own structural conventions.

24-ET representation. Used in this paper solely as a modern analytical approximation of neutral intervals; it does not imply historical tuning practice.

2. Construction

The Raised-Fifth Grid is derived from 12-tone equal temperament (12-ET). The system modifies the temperament by raising two pitch classes that form a fifth in 12-ET by 50 cents, while all remaining pitch classes retain their 12-ET positions. Figure 1 illustrates the resulting layout, with $E_{\flat}\uparrow$ and $A_{\flat}\uparrow$ raised by 50 cents.

Figure 1. 12-ET with the pitch-class offsets (+50 cents on $E_{\flat}\uparrow$ and $A_{\flat}\uparrow$).

The choice of which fifth to raise is arbitrary, since 12-ET is symmetrical. However, the direction of the shift is not: the pitch classes must be raised by 50 cents. Lowering them would generate a different and non-equivalent 10+2 layout—an inverted form of the Raised-Fifth Grid—on a fixed keyboard and would not allow the same modal mappings to

occur. The raised pitch classes introduce 150- and 250-cent steps, enabling the realization of certain Middle Eastern modal patterns (as approximated in 24-ET) within a fixed 12-key layout.

3. Middle Eastern Modal Pattern Mapping

In Middle Eastern music, modal structures are built from smaller interval-based units. In Arabic music theory these are called *jins*, while in Persian classical music comparable functions are served by *dang* and, at a more detailed level, *goushe*. Although these terms differ in function and theoretical scope, they all describe units defined by specific step patterns. In this paper, these step patterns are presented uniformly using the jins framework.

3.1 Jins Inventory

The Raised-Fifth grid supports jins, pl. *ajnas*, whose interval structures can be formed using whole, half, and neutral steps. These ajnas are possible from multiple positions on the grid whenever their internal step pattern is preserved. The supported patterns and an example pitch collection are listed in Table 1.

Ajnas	Step Pattern	Example	Possible from
Bayātī	3/4 3/4 W	D E♭↑ F G	D / G
Rast	W 3/4 3/4 W	C D E♭↑ F G	C / F
Kurd	H W W	E F G A	A / E / B / F# / C#
Hijāz	H A2 H	C D♭ E F	C / F / C# / F# / A
Lāmī	H W W H	E F G A B♭	E / B / F# / C#
‘Ajām	W W H W	C D E F G	C / D / F / G / A
Nahāwand	W H W W	A B C D E	D / E / G / A / B
‘Ajām Murassa‘	W W W H	F G A B C	F / C / G / B♭
Athar Kurd	H W A2 H	E F G A# B	F# / E / A# / B
Nikriz	W H A2 H	E F# G A# B	E / G / A# / B
Hijāz Murassa‘	H A2 H H	C D♭ E F G♭	C / F / C# / F#

Table 1. supported ajnas on the Raised-Fifth grid.

3.2 The Exceptional Pattern

The 10+2 grid also permits a step pattern not represented among the standard ajnas, shown in Table 2:

Step Pattern	Example	Possible from
3/4 5/4 H	D E♭↑ F# G	D / G

Table 2. exceptional pattern (3/4, 5/4, H).

This is the only pattern that uses the 5/4 step and occurs only from D and G in the 10+2 grid. It does not correspond to a named jins and appears in Persian dastgahs such as *Homāyūn* and *Chahārgāh*.

Section 3.3 Maqamat and Dastgah Mapping

Table 3 lists the maqamat and dastgahs supported by the Raised-Fifth grid, with their step patterns shown in ascending order.

Maqam & Dastgahs	Starting Pitch	Step Pattern	Pitch Content
Bayātī / Navā	D	3/4 3/4 W W H W W	D E♭↑ F G A B♭ C D
Shūr	D	3/4 3/4 W 3/4 3/4 W W	D E♭↑ F G A♭↑ B♭ C D
Rast	F	W 3/4 3/4 W W 3/4 3/4	F G A♭↑ B♭ C D E♭↑ F
Sīkāh / Segāh	A♭↑	3/4 W W 3/4 3/4 W 3/4	A♭↑ B♭ C D E♭↑ F G A♭↑
Şabā	D	3/4 3/4 H A2 H W W	D E♭↑ F G♭ A B♭ C D
Chahārgāh	D	3/4 5/4 H 3/4 5/4 H W	D E♭↑ F# G A♭↑ B C D
Homāyūn	G	3/4 5/4 H W 3/4 3/4 W	G A♭↑ B C D E♭↑ F G
Huzām	A♭↑	3/4 W H A2 H W 3/4	A♭↑ B♭ C D♭ E F G A♭↑
Nahāwand–Ĥijāz	D	W H W W H A2 H	D E F G A B♭ C# D
Ĥijāzkār – Nawā Athar	F	H A2 H W H A2 H	F G♭ A B♭ C D♭ E F
Ĥijāzkār Kurd	F#	H W W W H A2 H	F# G A B C# D E# F#
Athar Kurd	F#	H W A2 H H A2 H	F# G A B# C# D E# F#
Kurd	E	H W W W H W W	E F G A B C D E
ʿAjām / Māhūr	C	W W H W W W H	C D E F G A B C
Rastpanjgāh	C	W W H W W H W	C D E F G A B♭ C

Table 3. Supported maqāmāt and dastgāhs.

Including both dastgāhs and maqāmāt in Table 3 indicates only that their step patterns share the same 24-ET approximation within the 10+2 grid. The same step pattern may also appear under different modal names across traditions.

In Table 3, modal names connected with (–) indicate maqāmāt that share the same step pattern but arise from different starting pitches. For example, Nāhawand and Ĥijāz share the same step pattern corresponding to the harmonic minor scale; Nāhawand begins on the tonic, while Ĥijāz represents a rotation beginning on its fifth.

The (/) symbol is used when a Persian dastgāh and an Arabic maqām correspond to the same step pattern within the 10+2 grid.

Different modal names may share the same interval pattern but remain distinct modes due to tradition, function, and melodic practice.

Some maqām and dastgāh patterns may also occur from other degrees on the grid; for example, the Ḥijāzkār pattern shown from F is likewise available from F \sharp .

In Persian classical music, a single dastgāh does not always correspond to one fixed step pattern. Different traditions may assign distinct step patterns to the same modal name; for example, some lineages present *Shūr* with the same step pattern that also appears as *Bayātī/Navā* in related repertoires. Several modes also possess internal variants in which specific steps may shift between neutral and semitone values, as seen in certain forms of *Homāyūn*. Some of these variants remain compatible with the 10+2 grid but arise from different starting pitches. Table 3 therefore presents one representative pattern for each dastgāh, while acknowledging that additional traditional variants exist and may be crucial for the identity of the mode.

In both Persian and Arabic modal practice, maqāmāt and dastgāhs often extend beyond a single octave through characteristic upper-octave continuations. Some of these extensions are also realizable within the 10+2 grid. For example, in *Ḥijāzkār Kurd*, the grid supports not only the primary step pattern but also its upper-octave continuation, providing access to additional degrees such as G and B \flat .

4. Western Scalar Mapping

The 10+2 grid preserves the diatonic ordering of whole steps and semitones, allowing complete diatonic modal cycles to be formed from the pitch collections:

F–G–A–B \flat –C–D–E

C–D–E–F–G–A–B

G–A–B–C–D–E–F \sharp

D–E–F \sharp –G–A–B–C \sharp .

Each of these collections supports all seven diatonic modes (Ionian through Locrian).

Beyond the diatonic set, the grid also supports several additional heptatonic scalar types, summarized in Table 4.

Tonic	Harmonic Minor	Melodic Minor	Harmonic Major
G	-	✓	-
B	✓	-	-
D	✓	✓	✓
F	-	-	✓

Table 4. Supported Western heptatonic scale types.

The diatonic modes and the additional heptatonic scales listed in Table 4 are the only Western scales fully realizable on the 10+2 grid.

5. Conclusion

The Raised-Fifth Grid demonstrates that a single 50-cent displacement of one fifth within the 12-ET system is sufficient to support a wide range of Middle Eastern and Western modal

structures coexisting on a standard 12-key keyboard. The modal patterns realized in this system correspond to their standard 24-ET approximations, and Turkish modal structures that employ neutral intervals can likewise be mapped onto the grid. The unified 10+2 framework thus reveals both practical and pedagogical possibilities, enabling modes from different traditions to be accessed on a 12-key keyboard without dynamic retuning or additional keys, using only a minimum of twelve pitch classes per octave.

References

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